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Funding Panacea for the Development Information Communication Technology in Nigerian Schools

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Abstract: Purpose: *This paper explores the important of adequate funding of information communication technologies programme in the Nigerian schools.*

Method: *The paper is a review study. The paper depends on secondary data that were collected from government documents, print resources and online publication. Content analysis was used to narrow the literature to the theme of the study.*

Findings: *The paper revealed that adequate funding of information communication technologies programme in the schools in Nigeria will guarantee development of information communication technologies programme in the schools in Nigeria. Specifically, adequate funding of ICT programme will aid adequate provision of ICT facilities in schools; instillation of ICT infrastructure facilities and subsidization of cost of internet service in the schools. Based on this, the paper recommends that government and other stakeholders in education in Nigeria increase the budgetary allocation and improve their contributions to the development of ICT in the schools.*

Key words: *Funds, Information communication technology, Schools.*

Introduction

Poor funding remains one of the major problem facing the Nigeria' educational system. The poor funding appear to be facing all programme in the educational institutions. The poor budgetary

allocation to education appear to be responsible for poor development of academic subjects and programme in the schools.

Information communication technology is one of the academic programme in the educational institutions in Nigeria that is facing serious problem of funding. The programme is facing the problem of underfunding in all the forms of education in Nigeria. For instance, at the primary school education. Attah (2021) submitted that ICT programme is underfunded and this is responsible for the poor access to ICT facilities in the schools.

At the secondary school and tertiary institutions. Abara, Ogunode, and Olatunde-Aiyedun (2022) remarked that inadequate funding of public tertiary institutions in Nigeria affected the deployment of ICT during the COVID-19 era in the country. Many public tertiary institutions in Nigeria are underfunded. School administrators are not having access to adequate funds for the implementation of school programme. Many ICT facilities are not available in the institutions due to poor funding. Also, Edozie, Olibie, Eyiuche and Aghu, (2010); Deebom, & Zite, (2016) noted that inadequate funding of ICT programme in public Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) is a major factor that prevented many Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) from adopting virtual learning during the COVID-19 lock down in Nigeria. Olatunde-Aiyedun, Ogunode & Eyiolorunse-Aiyedun (2021) submitted that the inadequate funding is a major challenge to the administration of Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria. Jegede & Abashi (2019) observed that funding is the key to the successful implementation of ICT programs in the educational institution. The budgetary allocation for the implementation of computer education is inadequate in the basic schools and this is affecting the utilization of ICT facilities in the basics schools. To run or operate a computer system needs a lot of financial resources. School administrators of basic schools are not provided with adequate funds to manage the various ICF infrastructural under their cares.

Funding is vital for the implementation and success of any educational programme in the schools. Funding is the life wire and pillars that accelerated implementation of education programme like the ICT programme in the schools. It is based on this, that this study seeks to discuss the important of adequate funding of ICT programme in the Nigerian schools.

Literature Review

A school is a social institutions for implementation of teaching and learning and other extra-curriculum activities. A school is an institutions designed for impartation of knowledge. A school is a micro part of the society curve out for the purpose of teaching and learning. A school is a formal and non-formal institutions that brings together teachers, students and school administrators for the purpose of teaching and learning. A school is considered a second home for students, and teachers as a second set of parents.

The School is an organized social institutions meant for impartation of knowledge. The purpose or objective of the school is to provide a medium were instructors meet with learners to effect cane of behaviors. The School provide avenue for conducive teaching and learning to take place between the teachers, s and students. The Schools are designed to have service providers (school administrators, teachers and non-teaching staff) and services receiver (learners). The School stakeholders which include school administrators, teachers and non-teaching staff are providing services that demands tem to always upgrade their skills and knowledge.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is the integrated use of electronic tools and systems, including computers, telecommunications, and media technologies, that facilitate the

collection, storage, processing, transmission, and sharing of information. In educational settings, ICT encompasses a wide range of hardware, software, and networks that support various activities such as teaching, learning, administration, and research. These technologies enable users to access and manipulate data, enhance communication, and streamline processes, ultimately transforming the way information is delivered and received within institutions. ICT plays a vital role in modern education by improving access to knowledge, fostering collaboration, and promoting innovative learning experiences (Ogunode, Olatunde-Aiyedun, Ukozor, & Ayeni, 2024). For Shobowale, (2019) information and communication technology is a process of giving and getting information through the use of technologies like computers, internets, mobile phones and other communication networks. It includes all the technologies that help in disseminating and using information by individuals and institutions.

Information and Communication Technologies are those items which includes equipment known as (hardware) and programmes, known as (software) that allow people to access, organize, manipulate, retrieve, store, share and present information through electronic means (Adelakin 2009). ICT is a broad term that has to do with the harnessing of process, the methods and the product of electronic communication related technologies and other related resources in today's' knowledge driven society, for enhancing the productivity, the spread and efficiency of set programme activities geared towards the achievement of clearly defined goals. ICT and IT (Information Technology) are often used synonymously. However, the key difference is that IT is a subset of ICT which covers all forms of communication including telephone mobiles etc (Obanya 2009). United Nation Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2005) viewed ICT as the combination of all the computers, telecommunication and media technologies. They are also electronic technologies used for accessing, processing, gathering, manipulating and presenting or communicating information in education system.

Methods

The paper is a review study. The paper depends on secondary data that were collected from government documents, print resources and online publication. Content analysis was used to narrow the literature to the theme of the study.

Data Analysis on adequate funding of information communication Technologies

Proper funding of education and especially the ICT programme in the schools will guarantee sufficient funds for the internal management of ICT facilities and to constantly carry out maintenance on the facilities. Odufuwa (2012) and Patrick & Brenda (2018) maintained that adequate funding is needed to ensure full operation of ICT infrastructure facilities. Mooney, (2018) and Ogunode, Babayo, Jegede and Abubaka (2021) and James, Samuel and Ameh, (2015) noted that ICT operation and utilization is capital intensive and required properly funding to be able to maintain steady operation in the schools.

The high cost of internet services been complaint by students and teachers in the educational institutions can be subsidized by the government through adequate funding of the ICT programme in the schools. Many schools, teachers and students are not using their ICT facilities due to high cost of buying data and subscribe monthly. Provision of adequate funding for ICT programme in the schools help the schools to subsidize the cost and make the services accessible to the teachers and students (Ogunode, Adamu & Ajape 2021; Elujekwute, Shir, & Elujekwute, 2021).

Adequate funding of ICT programme in the schools in Nigeria will aid full implementation of ICT policies which will directly support development of ICT facilities and infrastructure facilities in the schools.

Government and the university management should inject more funds to support advanced training on ICT use for lecturers and students so as to improve their user experience (Aboki, Apuru & Lakan, (2023). Adequate budgetary allocation to schools and into ICT programme will help schools acquire computer facilities, telecommunication facilities, multimedia facilities, and internet facilities (Liverpool, & Jacinta, 2013; Khan, Khan, Din, Ismail, Khattak, & Jan 2015; Dada, Olowonefa, & Ogunode, 2022).

Adequate funding of ICT programme in the educational institutions across the country will assist the school administrators to employ adequate ICT professionals and expertise in the schools that will help to manage the ICT facilities and also provide instruction on ICT for the students (Nwosu, John, & Akorede, 2018). Increment in the budgetary allocation of ICT programme in the schools will help to improve the capacity of ICT teachers through effective organization of capacity building programme. ICT personnel in the schools needs training and retraining programme and it is only adequate funding can guarantee constant training for the ICT instructors in the schools (Oyekanmi, 2016; Ogunode, Abubakar, Abashi, Ireogbu & Longdet 202).

Findings

The paper showed that adequate funding of information communication technologies programme in the schools in Nigeria will aid development of information communication technologies programme in the schools in Nigeria. Also, adequate funding of ICT programme will support adequate provision of ICT facilities in schools; instillation of ICT infrastructure facilities and subsidization of cost of internet service in the schools.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper explores the important of adequate funding of information communication technologies programme in the Nigerian schools. The paper revealed that adequate funding of information communication technologies programme in the schools in Nigeria will guarantee development of information communication technologies programme in the schools in Nigeria. Specifically, adequate funding of ICT programme will aid adequate provision of ICT facilities in schools; instillation of ICT infrastructure facilities and subsidization of cost of internet service in the schools.

Based on this, the paper recommends that government and other stakeholders in education in Nigeria increase the budgetary allocation and improve their contributions to the development of ICT in the schools.

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